

OvidSP Medline search strategy

1. exp dexamethasone/
2. dexamethasone.af
3. exp dexmedetomidine
4. dexmedetomidine.af
5. 1 or 2
6. 3 or 4
7. 5 and 6

146 hits June 08, 2023

OvidSP Embase search strategy

1. exp dexamethasone/
2. dexamethasone.af
3. exp dexmedetomidine
4. dexmedetomidine.af
5. 1 or 2
6. 3 or 4
7. 5 and 6

943 hits June 08, 2023

CENTRAL

1. MeSH descriptor: [Dexmedetomidine] explode all trees
2. All text: (dexmedetomidine)
3. MeSH descriptor: [Dexamethasone] explode all trees
4. All text: (dexamethasone)
5. 1 or 2
6. 3 or 4
7. 5 and 6

280 hits June 08, 2023

Web of Science Core Collection

1. Dexmedetomidine (All Fields)
2. Dexamethasone (All fields)
3. 1 and 2

218 hits June 08, 2023

CINAHL

1. TX dexmedetomidine
2. TX dexamethasone
3. 1 and 2

213 hits June 08, 2023

BIOSIS

1. Dexmedetomidine (topic)
2. Dexamethasone (topic)
3. 1 and 2

32 hits June 08, 2023

ClinicalTrials.gov

Other terms: dexamethasone AND dexmedetomidine

76 hits June 08, 2023

EudraCT

Dexamethasone AND dexmedetomidine

1 hit June 08, 2023